

PICSE: Procurement Innovation for Cloud Services in Europe

*Funded under the EU Framework Programme for Research and innovation H2020
- Grant Agreement no: 644014*

Milestone Title: MS1 Communication Plan

Submission Due Date: M2 (November 2014)

Actual Submission Date: 20 November 2014

Work Package: WP1 (Coordination)

Responsible Partner: TRUST-IT

Distribution: Public

Nature: Milestone Report

Abstract: The purpose of this document is to define the focused communication and dissemination actions that the PICSE project will undertake to maximise PICSE's visibility and impact and to actively engage target audiences. The document also defines a set of key performance indicators to measure impact across all core activities.

This document produced by Members of the PICSE Partners and Consortium is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License. Permissions beyond the scope of this license may be available at <http://picse.eu/>. The PICSE project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 644014.

DOCUMENT INFORMATION

Project	
<i>Project acronym:</i>	PICSE
<i>Project full title:</i>	Procurement Innovation for Cloud Services in Europe
<i>Project start:</i>	1 October 2014
<i>Project duration:</i>	18 months
<i>Call:</i>	ICT-35-2014: Innovation and Entrepreneurship Support
<i>Grant agreement no.:</i>	644014
Document	
<i>Deliverable number:</i>	MS1
<i>Deliverable title:</i>	Communication Plan
<i>Author(s):</i>	Sara Garavelli, Nicholas Ferguson, Silvana Muscella (Trust-IT Services)
<i>Reviewer(s):</i>	PICSE Collaboration Board
<i>Work package no.:</i>	WP1
<i>Work package title:</i>	Coordination
<i>Work package leader:</i>	CERN
<i>Work package participants:</i>	CSA, TRUST-IT
<i>Distribution:</i>	Public
<i>Nature:</i>	Milestone Report
<i>Version/Revision:</i>	V1.0
<i>Draft/Final</i>	Final
<i>Keywords:</i>	Communication & Dissemination Plan, Stakeholders, Communication Tools, European Procurers’ Platform, Strategic alliances, Social Media Campaigns, Events, Webinars, Press and Media.

DISCLAIMER

PICSE (644014) is a Coordination and Support Action funded by the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation Horizon 2020. The PICSE Procurers’ Platform will give access to a unique repository of information supporting the move from outright purchase to ‘pay-per-usage’ made possible by the arrival of cloud computing. It builds on the Helix Nebula collaboration between supply and demand of which the three PICSE partners are key members.

This document contains information on PICSE core activities, findings and outcomes and it may also contain contributions from distinguished experts who contribute to PICSE. Any reference to content in this document should clearly indicate the authors, source, organisation and publication date. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the PICSE consortium and cannot be considered to reflect the views of the European Commission.

CHANGE LOG

Issue	Date	Description	Author/Partner
0.1	20 November 2014	First internal release	TRUST-IT (Garavelli/Ferguson/Muscella)
0.2	18 December 2014	Revised version including first partners & task force members feedback	TRUST-IT (Garavelli/Ferguson)
0.3	07 January 2015	Generic feedback on content and format	CERN (Amsaghrou/Jones)
1.0	08 January 2015	Final Release	TRUST-IT (Garavelli)

Table of Contents

1. Scope of PICSE Communication and Dissemination Strategy	7
2. Stakeholder identification and engagement	10
2.1 Stakeholder identification and engagement.....	10
2.1.1 Public Research Organisations (in particular actors involved in the procurement process).....	10
2.1.2 Libraries	11
2.1.3 Other Stakeholders.....	12
2.1.3.1 Procurement specialists (e.g. local government associations and procurement departments).....	12
2.1.3.2 Cloud service providers (CSP).....	12
2.1.3.3 Policy Makers	13
2.1.3.4 Public sector decision makers (local authorities, national government, public bodies)	14
2.1.3.5 Funding agencies.....	14
2.1.3.6 Initiatives working in the field of PCP / PPI	15
2.1.3.7 SMEs & the private sector.....	15
2.1.3.8 General public.....	15
2.2 Ensuring stakeholders complete the procurement model template for maximum outreach	16
3. PICSE Strategic Alliances	16
3.1 The PICSE partner network	16
3.2 The Helix Nebula Initiative.....	17
3.3 PICSE Task Force members.....	19
3.4 Other strategic initiatives	20
4. PICSE timely communication and promotion	21
4.1 The European Procurers’ Platform	22
4.1.1 PICSE Partner Search Facility.....	25
4.1.2 PICSE Procurement Wizard	26
4.2 Social media campaigns.....	26
4.2.1 LinkedIn	26
4.2.2 Twitter	27
4.3 Other communication tools.....	27
4.4 Events	28
4.4.1 PICSE Webinars	28
4.4.2 PICSE final event.....	29
4.4.3 External events	30
4.5 Communication Gannt	34
5. Outreach & visibility	35
5.1 Dissemination Database	35
5.2 Press & Media Channels	35
6. Development of a clear PICSE identity	37
7. Impact assessment.....	39

List of Figures

Figure 1: PICSE communication and dissemination activities.....9
Figure 2: PICSE Stakeholders.....10
Figure 3: PICSE Storytelling Template.....16
Figure 4: Detail of the www.picse.eu home page23
Figure 5: Cloudscape Gallery30
Figure 6: Communication and dissemination activities (M1-M18).....34
Figure 7: PICSE logo.....37

List of Tables

Table 1: Connection between PICSE goals and Communication and Dissemination objectives....8
Table 2: PICSE Task Force20
Table 3: Strategic Alliances.21
Table 4: PICSE web platform structure.....25
Table 5: PICSE Communication Tools.28
Table 6: PICSE External Events.33
Table 7: PICSE media channels.36
Table 7: PICSE promotional material.....38
Table 9: PICSE KPIs.39

Executive Summary

The PICSE Communication Plan provides the foundations on which the project defines and implements activities, supporting the goals and priorities of the project. This ensures effective engagement and interaction with the target communities leading to effective impact as the project evolves over time.

To this end, the Plan aims to be sufficiently flexible so as to ensure focused activities can be coordinated as event participation and other new opportunities arise.

The overall objectives of the PICSE communication and dissemination strategy can be summarized as follows:

This document explains the activities that will be carried out and the tools that will be implemented to achieve each of the above mentioned objectives. It also identifies major target audiences and outlines the consortium's extensive collective networks. Finally, it sets out measures that will be used to coordinate and monitor activities, including indicators to gauge impact.

A review of the progress achieved in implementing the Communication Plan will be made at mid-term of the project (month 9) as part of Milestone 5.

At the end of the project the overview of the results coming from the outreach activities will be described in the Final Dissemination and Exploitation Report (month 18). Dissemination and communication activities will be coordinated by WP1 and performed in all the WPs with the support of all the partners.

1. Scope of PICSE Communication and Dissemination Strategy

According to the European Cloud Strategy¹, the adoption of cloud computing in Europe will deliver a net gain of 2.5 million new European jobs, and an annual boost of EUR 160 billion to EU GDP (around 1%), by 2020, the timeframe of the PICSE project. PICSE wishes to contribute to this and will deliver services with a trans-national relevance: the procurement model, the analysis of the barriers to procurement of cloud services, the case studies, the procurement best practices report together with the final roadmap released by PICSE will have an important impact in the public sector by streamlining and optimising the procurement of cloud services.

The PICSE communication and dissemination strategy of PICSE has been developed with this overarching objective in mind.

The PICSE project will **set up a European Procurers’ Platform capable of raising the level of understanding on issues related to the procurement of cloud services**. Communication and dissemination activities will support the realization of this. Five main objectives have been identified as outlined below.

1. **Objective 1: Stakeholder identification and engagement** – Mobilization and engagement of target stakeholders: public research organizations (mainly all the actors involved in the procurement process), libraries, procurement specialists (in particular those dealing with the procurement of cloud services), cloud service providers, local government associations and procurement departments, initiatives working in the field of PCP / PPI, policy makers, funding agencies, public sector decision makers, SMEs & the private sector, general public;
2. **Objective 2: Establishing strategic alliances** - leveraging partner networks and strategic alliances in Europe and globally;
3. **Objective 3: Timely communication and promotion of the PICSE main outcomes² and of the opportunities offered by PCP/PPI actions** – Set up of an online repository of information, the European Procurers’ Platform (www.picse.eu), supporting the networking of procurers, promoting the cloud services market and facilitating the demand & supply side dialogue;
4. **Objective 4: Outreach & visibility of the project – Awareness raising activities to reach the biggest audience;**
5. **Objective 5: Developing a clear PICSE identity** – Design and development of a PICSE branding that is easily recognisable and facilitates the understanding of the PICSE findings and potential further exploitation. The creation of a strong identity will be helpful to create promotional & dissemination material on which PICSE can leverage on to disseminate the project findings at relevant events.

In detail, communication and dissemination activities will provide valuable support to achieving the project’s four specific goals as outlined below.

PICSE goal #1	Deliver a simpler procurement model for cloud services suited to the needs of a growing cross-disciplinary network of public research organizations. The procurement model will be supported by the delivery of a self-assessment tool that public procurers can use to evaluate their current procurement process (focus on cloud services) and by a Procurement Wizard able to facilitate public research organizations
---------------	--

¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/european-cloud-computing-strategy>

² Best Practices Report, the new procurement model, the trans-national case studies, the final roadmap, the issues surrounding procurement of cloud services.

	<p>in buying cloud services.</p> <p>Communication and Dissemination objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Set up of a clear stakeholder engagement strategy to identify and involve the main stakeholders (including also PICSE Task Force members) in the development of the procurement model. • Engage public research organisations to validate the PICSE procurement model through the analysis of specific case studies by collecting their testimonies. • Raise Awareness on the new procurement model and the trans-national case studies through outreach & dissemination activities including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ an online unique repository of information (the European Procurers’ Platform) supporting the networking of procurers. ○ Webinars to educate procurers on the new PICSE model • Build an online community focused on procurement issues • Release a Procurement Wizard as a decision support tool that can guide the procurer via a series of multiple choice questions, to identify suitable options and highlight key aspects that should be taken into account during the procurement process.
PICSE goal #2	<p>Provide a range of best practices for implementing results</p> <p>Communication and Dissemination objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and promote procurement best practices (mainly focused on procurement of cloud services but also procurement best practices related to other field that can be adopted as reference model) and focusing on how the various end-user requirements are met • Create Awareness on the best practices and issues surrounding procurement of cloud services through the European Procurers’ Platform • Perform outreach & dissemination activities to give visibility to ensure the best practices reach European stakeholders
PICSE goal #3	<p>Set out a realistic roadmap for cloud procurement over the next five years</p> <p>Communication and Dissemination objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bring together all the relevant stakeholders and involve them in the development of the final roadmap. • Ensure a dissemination of the final roadmap to support uptake of recommendations, involving also policy makers, funding agencies and public bodies’ decision makers.
PICSE goal #4	<p>Lay the foundations for future joint procurements, PCP and PPI actions</p> <p>Communication and Dissemination objectives:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Speed up the procurement of cloud services in Europe by creating a network of procurers and suppliers willing to participate in PPI³/PCP⁴ actions. • Ensure an effective dialogue between supply and the demand side. • Offer a knowledge repository where all the actors potentially involved in future joint procurements, PCP, PPI actions can find useful and updated information on PCP/PPI, ICT8 call, etc.

Table 1: Connection between PICSE goals and Communication and Dissemination objectives

³ Public Procurement for Innovation

⁴ Pre-Commercial Procurement

Communication & Dissemination Activities	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18
PICSE Procurement Model Release																		
PICSE Procurement Model Interim Release																		
<i>Engagement of the Task Force Members & key stakeholders to validate the Interim model (specific email campaign)</i>																		
<i>Creation of an animated video describing the PICSE procurement model</i>																		
<i>Press Release on the new Procurement Model & the Procurement Wizard</i>																		
<i>Article on iSGTW (promoting the model and the video - Video of the week)</i>																		
<i>Launch of the Procurement Wizard within the PICSE website & Cloud Watch Mobile App</i>																		
Procurement Barriers Report																		
<i>Preparation of the barriers survey</i>																		
<i>Identification of the right channels to promote the barriers survey</i>																		
<i>Preparation of communication messages to invite key stakeholders to complete the barriers survey</i>																		
<i>Promotion of the barriers survey</i>																		
<i>Publication of the barriers survey results on the PICSE website</i>																		
<i>Promotion of the findings of the barriers survey - press release</i>																		
Procurement Case Studies																		
<i>Identification of 5 case studies (population of the Diss & Comm db & engagement of new communities)</i>																		
<i>1 Phone/written interview per month with representatives of public sector organisations</i>																		
<i>Creation of an animated video illustrating the main results collected through the case studies analysis</i>																		
<i>Press Release on the new Procurement Model & Best Practice Report</i>																		
<i>Article on iSGTW (promoting the model and the video - Video of the week)</i>																		
Procurement Best Practices Report																		
Procurement Best Practices Report Interim Document																		
<i>Publication of the best practice report on the PICSE website</i>																		
Roadmap																		
<i>Press Release on the final Roadmap</i>																		
<i>Identification of the key stakeholders and media channels for the Roadmap promotion</i>																		
<i>Preparation of communication messages for the different stakeholders focused on the PICSE roadmap. The messages will be sent via email to try to maximize the impact and exploitation of the roadmap results</i>																		

Figure 1: PICSE communication and dissemination activities.

This document summarizes all the activities that will be performed to achieve each objective and the expected impact.

2. Stakeholder identification and engagement

2.1 Stakeholder identification and engagement

Building on the collaborative model adopted in Helix Nebula in bringing together supply and demand, PICSE will engage with providers and customers for cloud services over a crucial eighteen month period in which results from the Cloud Strategy actions emerge and several large multinational procurements (including PPIs and PCPs) take place.

Figure 2: PICSE Stakeholders.

Tables below identifies PICSE target stakeholders and the mutual benefits of collaboration with the project.

2.1.1 Public Research Organisations (in particular actors involved in the procurement process)

<p>How PICSE can contribute</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support in moving towards procurement of cloud services by leveraging the procurement model defined exploiting the experiences of the public research organizations involved in the Helix Nebula Initiative. • Visibility through the publication of procurement best practices on PICSE website. • PICSE is also the place where they can meet the supply side and build an interactive dialogue. • Opportunity to use the ICT8, ICT36 (focus on cloud) Partner Search facility. • Education on the procurement of cloud services best practices and current barriers through the Procurement best practices report and the Barriers of procurement of cloud services report and the webinars that will be performed during the project
--	--

	duration.
How PICSE can benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The engagement of the public research organizations involved in Helix Nebula will be beneficial for PICSE to have direct interlocutors for the development of the procurement self-assessment tool and the procurement wizard. They will validate the self-assessment tool and the wizard by providing feedback and be fundamental to provide trans-national case studies. • The engagement of other public research organizations outside Helix Nebula will be helpful to PICSE to further validate the model and to engage new communities. • Provision of examples of successful (and not) procurement of cloud services, feedback on challenges, and feedback on PICSE outcomes. • Contribution to collection of challenges to procurement.
Priority of engagement	High
Stakeholders identified at month 2⁵	CERN ⁶ , EMBL ⁷ ESA ⁸ DLR ⁹ , PIC ¹⁰ , ECMWF ¹¹ , ESRF ¹² , ESFRI projects, GRNET ¹³ , Umeå University ¹⁴
Engagement actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The public research organizations involved in Helix Nebula will validate the case study template developed by PICSE and will be the first to complete it through dedicated interviews. • These organizations will also contribute to PICSE webinars to showcase procurement best practices. • PICSE to contact other public research organizations, external to Helix Nebula, with targeted messages and invite them to complete the case study template and the barriers survey. • PICSE to encourage contributions to ICT Call 8 partner search. • Invitation to PICSE events to provide feedback on project findings and the final Cloud Service Procurement Roadmap.

2.1.2 Libraries

How PICSE can contribute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support libraries in moving towards procurement of cloud services by leveraging on the procurement model, the analysis of the barriers to procurement of cloud services, the case studies, the procurement best practices report together with the final roadmap released by PICSE. • Visibility through the publication of procurement best practices on PICSE website. • PICSE is also the place where they can meet the supply side and build an interactive dialogue. • Opportunity to use the ICT8, ICT36 (focus on cloud) Partner Search facility.
How PICSE can benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The engagement of libraries will be beneficial for PICSE to collect different perspectives and needs from public sector. Libraries share similar needs of the scientific communities thus some commonalities can be identified in the procurement of cloud services. • Contribution to collection of challenges to procurement.
Priority of engagement	High
Stakeholders identified at	Association of European Research Libraries – LIBER ¹⁶ , League of European Research

⁵ Stakeholders will be continuously identified over the project life time

⁶ <http://home.web.cern.ch/>

⁷ European Molecular Biology Laboratory

⁸ European Space Agency

⁹ <http://www.dlr.de/dlr/en/desktopdefault.aspx/tabid-10002/>

¹⁰ <http://www.pic.es/>

¹¹ <http://www.ecmwf.int/>

¹² <http://www.esrf.eu/>

¹³ <https://www.grnet.gr/>

¹⁴ <http://www.umu.se/english>

month 2¹⁵	Universities - LERU ¹⁷ , Research Data Netherlands ¹⁸
Engagement actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PICSE to contact libraries in Europe with targeted messages and invite them to perform interviews to collect their challenges in procuring cloud services and complete the case study template and the barriers survey. • They will be contacted to validate the procurement self assessment tool and wizard. • PICSE to encourage contributions to ICT Call 8 partner search. • Invitation to PICSE events to provide feedback on project findings and the final Cloud Service Procurement Roadmap.

2.1.3 Other Stakeholders

2.1.3.1 Procurement specialists (e.g. local government associations and procurement departments)

How PICSE can contribute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Even if the primary focus of PICSE is on the public sector and in particular scientific research, the Procurement Best Practices, the Case Studies and the Cloud Service Procurement Roadmap for public research organisations can help procurers from other sectors understand how to design their procurement model and how to address challenges they are facing. • PICSE outcomes such as the Procurement Best Practices and the Cloud Service Procurement Roadmap can help provide added-value services to members of associations of procurers and local governments. • The Partner Search facility set up can help stakeholders in creating new partnerships for the ICT8 & ICT36 (focus on cloud).
How PICSE can benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provision of examples of procurement practices, of feedback on the major barriers encountered or comments on the PICSE outcomes. • Potential multipliers of PICSE impact and channel to transfer PICSE knowledge to their communities (in case of procurers associations).
Priority of engagement	Medium
Stakeholders identified at month 2¹⁹	EuroCIO procurers group, ICLEI ²⁰ - Local Governments for Sustainability, C4BI ²¹ , http://openforumeurope.org/openprocurement
Engagement actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invitation to complete the PICSE barriers survey • Engagement on PICSE partner search in order to establish new PCP/PPI actions. • Invitation to PICSE events and provision of feedback on project findings and on the final Cloud Service Procurement Roadmap. • Contact for interest in information services (focused on procurement of cloud services) that they can provide to their members through PICSE. • PICSE results will be made available for their community together with the dissemination of PICSE events.

2.1.3.2 Cloud service providers (CSP)

How PICSE can contribute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thanks to the documents delivered by PICSE, cloud service providers will have a better understanding of the needs and the main issues encountered by public
---------------------------------	---

¹⁶ <http://libereurope.eu/>

¹⁵ Stakeholders will be continuously identified over the project life time

¹⁷ <http://www.leru.org/>

¹⁸ <http://www.researchdata.nl/en>

¹⁹ Stakeholders will be continuously identified over the project life time

²⁰ www.iclei.org

²¹ www.procurers-network.com

	<p>research organizations in procuring cloud services. This acquired knowledge will help providers to refine their contracts and their current approach in selling cloud services thus to facilitate their customers from the public sector and increase their spending.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thanks to PICSE, cloud providers have the opportunity to showcase their innovative solutions through the Partner Search facility, by increasing the awareness around their services and their market. • PICSE is also the place where CSPs can meet the demand side and build an interactive dialogue.
How PICSE can benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement with cloud providers will help PICSE to become a reference point for the procurers of cloud services maximizing its impact. • The Partner Search section of the PICSE web platform aimed to collect the information on the most innovative cloud services will help PICSE to contribute to create a Single Digital Market as hoped for the Europe’s Digital Agenda.
Priority of engagement	Medium
Stakeholders identified at month 2²²	European CSPs will be targeted including both large and small companies, Canopy ²³ , CloudSigma ²⁴ , Interoute ²⁵ , Memset ²⁶ , SAP ²⁷ , Sixsq ²⁸ , T-Systems ²⁹ , The Server Labs ³⁰ , Ultimum Technologies ³¹ , Capgemini ³² , DataCentred ³³ , DEAC ³⁴ , Nephos ³⁵ , Orange Business Solutions ³⁶ , Prologue ³⁷ , Telefonica ³⁸ , Thales ³⁹ , Yandex ⁴⁰
Engagement actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CSPs will be invited to take part to the PICSE events to provide feedback on the project findings and on the final Cloud Service Procurement Roadmap.

2.1.3.3 Policy Makers

How PICSE can contribute	PICSE provides a platform for dialogue on cloud service procurement procedures contributing to the growth of the European economy.
How PICSE can benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Act as multipliers of the PICSE impact. • PICSE can leverage events organized by the EC on procurement of cloud services to engage new stakeholders.
Priority of engagement	Medium
Stakeholders identified at month 2⁴¹	Relevant EC units, Member states (i.e Ministries of research & Innovation, of development)
Engagement actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The final roadmap can contribute to development of standardised procurement procedures on an EU level for the public sector.

²² Stakeholders will be continuously identified over the project life time

²³ canopy-cloud.com

²⁴ www.cloudsigma.com

²⁵ www.interoute.com

²⁶ www.memset.com

²⁷ www.sap.com

²⁸ sixsq.com

²⁹ www.t-systems.com

³⁰ www.theserverlabs.com

³¹ ultimumtechnologies.com

³² www.capgemini.com

³³ datacentred.co.uk

³⁴ www.deac.eu

³⁵ www.nephotechnologies.com

³⁶ www.orange-business.com

³⁷ www.prologue.fr/en/

³⁸ www.telefonica.com

³⁹ www.thalesgroup.com

⁴⁰ www.yandex.com

⁴¹ Stakeholders will be continuously identified over the project life time

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation to the events organized under the rotating Presidency of the European Union
--	---

2.1.3.4 Public sector decision makers (local authorities, national government, public bodies)

How PICSE can contribute	The PICSE procurement practices and the Cloud Service Procurement Roadmap can raise awareness on benefits of cloud computing.
How PICSE can benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Act as promoters of PICSE user experiences and the adoption of the PICSE roadmap recommendations. They can also contribute to PICSE webinars to showcase procurement best practices for government.
Priority of engagement	Medium
Stakeholders identified at month 2⁴²	UK government, Australian government, Dutch government
Engagement actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project outcomes to be disseminated to and through them. PICSE will use Government procurement practices to identify commonalities with the public research organizations best practices but also as examples to for the science public sector.

2.1.3.5 Funding agencies

How PICSE can contribute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thanks to PICSE, funding agencies would be able to seize opportunities from more cost effective and innovative public procurement practices which they can disseminate across their national stakeholders. The Procurement Best Practices, the Case Studies and the Cloud Service Procurement Roadmap for public research organisations will help them understand the potential impact of procuring cloud services and the pay-per-use model. The output of PICSE can also be directly relevant for the future work programme for DG CONNECT and DG RESEARCH & INNOVATION to understand if the actions put in place by the DGs on procurement of cloud services can effectively and concretely help the advances of public sector in this field. It can also be an important input for the European Cloud Computing Strategy by providing concrete examples of use cases, proposing adapted procurement models, collecting draft technical specifications and making detailed assessments of the market potential for cloud services in the public research sector. Finally, the results will also have a direct impact on the work of the European Cloud Partnership (ECP) and its plans to establish a Trusted Cloud Europe framework to support the definition of common cloud best practices, linking them to use cases, and applying them in practice.
How PICSE can benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promotion of the cost effective and innovative public procurement best practices identified by PICSE and of the adoption of the PICSE roadmap recommendations. PICSE can leverage on the events organised by the DGs.
Priority of engagement	Medium
Stakeholders identified at month 2⁴³	EC, European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST), National research agencies and councils in EU28
Engagement actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The PICSE final roadmap will be dispatched to funding agencies, national research agencies & councils and to the related intergovernmental framework for European Cooperation in Science and Technology (COST) PICSE best practices will be disseminated through the funding agencies channels (i.e. CORDIS). Invitation to take part at PICSE events and provide feedback on project findings

⁴² Stakeholders will be continuously identified over the project life time

⁴³ Stakeholders will be continuously identified over the project life time

	<p>including the final Cloud Service Procurement Roadmap.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> PICSE will present the main results at events related to procurement of cloud services organised by the DGs
--	---

2.1.3.6 Initiatives working in the field of PCP / PPI

How PICSE can contribute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support them with the outcomes coming from the PICSE Best Practices and Barriers report, the new procurement model and best practices report and the final roadmap Opportunity for visibility through publication of news, best practices and success stories on PICSE web platform.
How PICSE can benefit	Act as multipliers of the PICSE impact and channel for transfer of PICSE knowledge to communities.
Priority of engagement	Medium
Stakeholders identified at month 2⁴⁴	Cloud for Europe ⁴⁵ , G-Cloud ⁴⁶ , Procurement Forum ⁴⁷
Engagement actions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PICSE results and activities disseminated to communities Invitation to take part in PICSE events and provide feedback on project findings and the final Cloud Service Procurement Roadmap.

2.1.3.7 SMEs & the private sector

How PICSE can contribute	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Potential for sharing of PICSE results for adoption of standardized procedures by SME sector. PICSE recommendations can facilitate SMEs in applying for public procurement actions in the future.
How PICSE can benefit	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Act as multipliers of the PICSE impact. Response by SMEs to the PICSE barriers survey.
Priority of engagement	Low
Engagement actions	PICSE to engage with SME associations and National Trade Associations in order to showcase results and invite SMEs to contribute to PICSE barriers survey

2.1.3.8 General public

How PICSE can contribute	They can find in PICSE a useful source of information on innovative procurement of cloud services and practices.
How PICSE can benefit	They can be multipliers of the PICSE impact.
Priority of engagement	Low
Engagement actions	They can benefit from the knowledge generated by the project directly accessing the PICSE online platform. Dissemination efforts will be oriented also in this direction.

In order to keep track and contact with individuals from each stakeholder groups, PICSE will create a stakeholder database. Trust-IT will store all relevant contacts with information on Name, Surname, Position, Organisation, Organisation Type, Stakeholder category, Involvement in PICSE, Specific Engagement Actions. This database will be a document evolving over the life-cycle of the project. The first contacts to be collected will be relevant stakeholders from the Helix Nebula initiative and the PICSE Task Force.

⁴⁴ Stakeholders will be continuously identified over the project life time

⁴⁵ www.cloudforeurope.eu

⁴⁶ <https://www.gov.uk/how-to-use-cloudstore>

⁴⁷ <https://procurement-forum.eu/>

2.2 Ensuring stakeholders complete the procurement model template for maximum outreach

In developing the PICSE procurement model the partners will prepare five case studies of cloud service procurement (T2.2). These will be analysed and the main outcomes will feed into the PICSE roadmap.

A case study reference framework will be prepared to ensure that the case study template can be adopted as working instrument by procurers, even after the end of the project. Information part of the case study that can be made public will be published on the PICSE website.

In addition to the five case studies, PICSE will collect a series of less detailed best practices that will enrich the PICSE knowledge repository. The objective of this activity is to showcase how procurement challenges have been addressed. These will be presented in an easily accessible and attractive template as shown below.

Figure 3: PICSE Storytelling Template.

3. PICSE Strategic Alliances

3.1 The PICSE partner network

The establishment of strategic alliances within PICSE will be facilitated by the extensive network of contacts of the PICSE partners. Their network will be exploited as part of the communication and dissemination strategy to spread the knowledge about PICSE results and main achievements.

In particular, **CERN**, who is the world’s largest particle physics lab, will be the main interface to engage the **Helix Nebula** partners but also **other public research organisations** that are facing the same issues with the procurement of cloud services. On 1st February 2013 CERN hosted a workshop on the IT requirements for the next generation research infrastructures within the CRISP project: **Cluster of Research Infrastructures**

for Synergies in Physics (CRISP <http://www.crisp-fp7.eu/>). CRISP is a cooperative project which builds collaborations and creates long-term synergies between research infrastructures on the ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructure) Roadmap in the field of physics, astronomy and analytical facilities to facilitate their implementation and enhance their efficiency and attractiveness. CRISP's mission is to encourage and enable collaborating partners to combine their know-how and complementary expertise in an effective manner. This event was a first step to discuss with the ESFRI projects about procurement plans. If the IT needs of the RIs can be sufficiently aligned, the approaches of pre-commercial procurement (PCP) and public procurement of innovative solutions (PPI: a step following pre-commercial procurement) could offer a means for creating a market opportunity with sufficient interest to encourage the IT industry to develop suitable products.

The **Cloud Security Alliance** (CSA) will leverage on its **global organisation** to promote the PICSE best practices and results to its over 70,000 individual members and to the current 22 global research initiatives in cloud computing security best practice and compliance in which is involved such as **CUMULUS, SPECS, A4Cloud and Cirrus**. CSA also serves on the SLA Cloud Select Industry Groups (C-SIGs) and provides PICSE with strong links into the implementation of the EU Cloud Strategy. The CSA annual congress will be leveraged to promote PICSE results.

Trust-IT is currently the Coordinator of **CloudWATCH**, (www.cloudwatchhub.eu) which is promoting best practices on interoperable clouds, building common standards profiles, providing recommendations for certification and practical legal tips on contractual and data protection issues. A strong synergy between CloudWatch and PICSE will be created: PICSE can leverage on CloudWATCH events to promote its results and gain visibility in Europe through the consolidated [cloudwatchhub.eu](http://www.cloudwatchhub.eu). PICSE can contribute to CloudWATCH enriching its knowledge repository on the topic of procurement of cloud services. The PICSE Procurement Wizard could also be integrated into the CL application.

In addition Trust-IT spearheaded the high-profile **cloudscapeseries.eu** in 2009, successfully transforming it into a self-sustained event since 2014. With the support of a distinguished Programme Committee, Cloudscape attracts top-level experts from across the globe, offering insights into current and future directions, including international policy dialogue support. PICSE will leverage on Cloudscape events to communicate his results. PICSE plans to have its finale event in conjunction with Cloudscape VIII (2016).

From January 2015, Trust-IT will coordinate, for 24 months and partner in two projects one around the delivery of Service Level Agreements for Europe entitled SLA-Ready which deals with Cloud contracts and Service Level Agreements (SLAs) are key components defining cloud services. This can certainly lead to concrete synergies and actions here. CLARUS, instead, looks to improve trust in cloud computing services by developing a secure framework for the storage and processing of data outsourced to the cloud that allows end users to monitor, audit and retain control of the stored data without impairing the functionality and cost-saving benefits of cloud services. Both projects lead to key end-results to serve each of the stakeholders in PICSE.

3.2 The Helix Nebula Initiative

Each PICSE partner is a member of the Helix Nebula Initiative (www.helix-nebula.eu). Helix Nebula is a partnership between the private sector providers of cloud services and the public sector operators of data-intensive research infrastructures in areas such as high energy physics, earth-observation and microbiology.

Helix Nebula demonstrated the potential of a hybrid model bringing together service providers, research organisations, data providers and publicly funded e-infrastructures, notably GEANT and EGI, to support and transform publicly funded research into data driven knowledge that is valuable to the wider research community and downstream industries. The stakeholders have federated their efforts and resources

permitting the suppliers to develop a first product called HNX1 that is being marketed in a range of business sectors. In parallel the European Cloud Partnership (ECP)⁴⁸ is working to bring together industry and the public sector to establish a Digital Single Market for cloud computing in Europe. The ECP publication “Establishing a Trusted Cloud Europe”⁴⁹ highlights the role of Helix Nebula. Helix Nebula in turn wishes to make use of ECP’s work on the contractual aspects of delivering cloud services including services level agreements, certification requirements, a code of conduct, and terms and conditions that respect European legislation. The situation described above highlights the **lack of a single focal point** to bring together Europe’s developments, federating capacity, policy and **procurement activities** into a consistent whole that can remove fragmentation and ensure the results of each activity are fully exploited.

The work performed during the Helix Nebula initiative during its two years pilot phase has shown that **cloud services are suitable for scientific workloads performed by public research organisations and they are now prepared to consider procuring commercial cloud services on a significant scale.**

PICSE will start from the analysis of the Helix Nebula flagships with additional input coming from a set of public research organisations that have already expressed their interest in the Helix Nebula initiative (i.e. PIC, ECMWF, UNESCO, DG DIGIT and JRC) to develop the innovative procurement model for public research organisations.

In addition, within the Helix Nebula consortium, a number of public research organisations have provided letters of support to the initiative on the understanding that the services will be made available on a commercial basis. These public research organisations will be one of the **key groups of the PICSE Procurers’ Network and include:**

- The European Centre for Nuclear Research (CERN)
- The Centre National d'Etudes Spatiales (CNES)
- The Institute for Electromagnetic Sensing of the Environment (IREA) of the National Research Council (CNR)
- The Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR)
- The European Molecular Biology Laboratory (EMBL)
- The European Bioinformatics Institute (EMBL-EBI)
- The European Space Agency (ESA)
- The Department Port d'Informació Científica (PIC) of the Institut de Física d'Altes Energies (IFAE)

Public research organisations, representing both international and national research agencies, have prior experience of cross-border procurements. The international research organisations have selected three flagship use cases, which are being used to assess, evaluate and benchmark their respective ICT service needs. This will provide the initial data for the procurement model and ensure that the model has a European-wide dimension:

- The CERN - ATLAS use case evaluates the use of cloud technologies for the ATLAS data processing, integrates cloud computing resources with the existing ATLAS distributed grid based computing software and services, and implements the ATLAS cloud computing model within its distributed data management, production and analysis system, as well as related tools and services.

⁴⁸ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/european-cloud-partnership>

⁴⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/news/trusted-cloud-europe>

- EMBL is broadening the scope of large-scale genomic analysis while limiting capital investments in computing infrastructure. The necessity here is to provide data storage coupled with processing of a complex workflow, which is elastic enough to meet the growing demand for computing power.
- Through its SuperSites Exploitation Platform use case (SSEP), ESA is building an open source, unified ecosystem with improved data products for solid earth data research, providing secure sharing of data, and enabling international collaboration within a larger user base to improve understanding of the phenomena.

The sponsors of these use cases, as public organisations, are subject to divergent jurisdictions and independent procurement processes.

The connection with Helix Nebula will be also fundamental to achieve the communication objectives mentioned in chapter 1. In particular:

- Helix Nebula public research organizations partners will be fundamental to validate and improve the procurement model for cloud services developed by PICSE.
- Use cases collected will come from Helix Nebula. Interviews with the public research organizations will be conducted and the main findings will be published on the European Procurers’ Platform as examples for other institutions.
- The big network of cloud service providers federated by Helix Nebula will become part of the PICSE environment. Through the PICSE platform they will have the opportunity to showcase their cloud solutions and the Helix Nebula products by reaching potential new customers.
- The Helix Nebula General Assembly Events will become important milestones for PICSE as the project will have the opportunity to leverage on these events to present its outcomes and collect feedback.
- All the actors participating in Helix Nebula will be multipliers of the PICSE visibility by being ambassadors of PICSE outcomes towards other stakeholders.

3.3 PICSE Task Force members

PICSE has assembled a pool of experts to form the PICSE Task Force. This expert group is chartered with providing consultation and strategic advice to the PICSE consortium. Active throughout the lifetime of the project, the PICSE Task Force will act as an important sounding-board capable of eliciting the opinions of important stakeholder groups. The group will be also fundamental to raise full awareness of procurement of cloud services & promote best practices helping to increase the project impact.

The table below shows the current members who have agreed to join the group. This current group will remain in a fluid state with new members invited to join and participate if and when deemed necessary by the consortium.

Task Force Member	Relevance to PICSE
Martin Canning, Group Vice President,	International Data Corporation (IDC) is a global provider of market intelligence, advisory services, and events for the information technology, telecommunications and consumer

European Consulting, International Data Corporation	technology markets. IDC helps IT professionals, business executives, and the investment community make fact-based decisions on technology purchases and business strategy. Martin manages IDC's consulting and custom research business in Western Europe and is responsible for the delivery of client projects across all areas of IDC's IT markets coverage. With his experience he can provide useful feedback and information of the procurement model best practices in Europe so contributing to the PICSE final roadmap. He will be also the facilitator to disseminate PICSE and its event through the IDC website (www.idc.com).
James Mitchell, CEO at Strategic Blue, trader of Cloud Options, a TechStars company focussed on financial cloud brokerage	James founded Strategic Blue to offer "Cloud Options" - the billing and price risk management solutions for corporate users of public Cloud Computing Infrastructure as a Service. James can contribute to the PICSE roadmap with his huge experience in cloud pricing and in understanding the key aspects when buying cloud solutions (www.cloudoptions.com). James Mitchell is also author of the article "Cloud Pricing is Broken" curated by The Economist Intelligence Unit.
Linda Strick, Cloud for Europe & Fraunhofer-Institute FOKUS	Linda is the coordinator of the Cloud for Europe (www.cloudforeurope.eu) project. Cloud for Europe supports public sector cloud use as collaboration between public authorities and industry. The project identifies obstacles, finds innovative solutions and builds trust in European cloud computing. Cloud for Europe uses pre-commercial procurement as an instrument for public sector innovation. She can bring to PICSE the experience matured in Cloud for Europe and her expertise in the domain of eGovernment and public innovation. Her participation will facilitate a coordinated approach to interrelated activities between the two projects and the participation at mutual outreach events. Fraunhofer has also a large Public Administration network in Germany,
Frank van Dam, Enterprise IT Architect & IT Consultant, Ministry of Economic Affairs, The Netherlands	Frank Can contribute to PICSE with its valuable experience of cloud services for the public sector. Franck contributed to the ENISA Good Practice guide for securely deploying Governmental Clouds ⁵⁰ , a guide for public bodies providing recommendations on the definition of their security and resilience requirements and on how to evaluate and choose from the different Cloud computing service delivery models. He can bring to PICSE the perspective of a public body.

Table 2: PICSE Task Force.

3.4 Other strategic initiatives

During the project lifetime PICSE will establish synergies also with other relevant European and global initiatives that can contribute to the PICSE outputs and also benefit from its results. Table below reports the relevant initiatives identified at M2. The table will be updated during the project lifetime.

Initiatives	How PICSE can contribute	How PICSE can benefit
A4Cloud (http://www.a4cloud.eu/)	A4Cloud can exploit the results of the PICSE Roadmap.	PICSE can leverage some of the requirements and practices proposed in A4Cloud in the definition of the procurement best practices.
Cloud for Europe (www.cloudforeurope.eu)	PICSE can promote the open tender published by Cloud for Europe and increase awareness on Pre commercial procurement.	Some of the results and the deliverables of Cloud for Europe can be relevant for PICSE. Interviews with the members of the initiative will be really helpful to gain understanding of the issues encountered

⁵⁰ <http://www.enisa.europa.eu/activities/Resilience-and-CIIP/cloud-computing/good-practice-guide-for-securely-deploying-governmental-clouds>

		in the process of the tender definition.
G-Cloud (https://www.gov.uk/how-to-use-cloudstore)	PICSE can provide procurement of cloud services best practices related to public research organisations and libraries that could be appropriate also for government.	PICSE can understand what are the best practices and the UK government approach to a cloud marketplace and identify the best practices that could apply to the public research sector. G-Cloud can become part of the PICSE case studies.
Open standards for ICT procurement	PICSE can bring insights on the procurement of cloud services issues and challenges.	PICSE can find public sector organisations that can contribute to the case studies and gain understanding on how standards impact on ICT procurement.
The Research Data Alliance - RDA (https://rd-alliance.org/)	PICSE can bring insights on the procurement of cloud services issues and challenges to the following Working and Interest Groups: Development of cloud computing capacity and education in developing world research ⁵¹ Federated Identity Management ⁵² , Service Management IG ⁵³ , RDA/CODATA Legal Interoperability IG ⁵⁴ , Brokering IG ⁵⁵ , Brokering Governance ⁵⁶ . The most relevant groups will be selected during the lifetime of the project.	PICSE can benefit from the international dialogue with high-level experts.

Table 3: Strategic Alliances.

4. PICSE timely communication and promotion

Timely communication and promotion of the PICSE main outcomes and of the opportunities offered by PCP/PPI actions is one of the main objectives of the PICSE communication strategy.

The main communication tool that will be used to achieve this objective will be the PICSE web platform (www.picse.eu). It will become a unique online repository of information, the European Procurers' Platform, capable of supporting the networking of procurers, promoting the cloud services market and facilitating the demand & supply side dialogue. The European Procurers' Platform will also help those involved in procurement to understand the implications of ongoing work under the cloud computing strategy.

In addition to the PICSE web platform other communication tools will be put in place to ensure the timely communication around Cloud Service Procurement best practices, barriers, innovative aspects and the

⁵¹ <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/development-cloud-computing-capacity-and-education-developing-world-research.html>

⁵² <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/federated-identity-management.html>

⁵³ <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/service-management-ig.html>

⁵⁴ <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/rdacodata-legal-interoperability-ig.html>

⁵⁵ <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/brokering-ig.html>

⁵⁶ <https://rd-alliance.org/groups/brokering-governance.html>

importance of their adoption for the public sector with a focus on research, including of course the final Roadmap.

A variety of formats will be used such as Social Media Campaigns, Interviews, and Events.

4.1 The European Procurers' Platform

PICSE aims to consolidate its work by setting up a **European Procurers' Platform** capable of raising the level of understanding on issues surrounding procurement of cloud services, especially with initial use cases from the science domain.

The PICSE Procurers' Platform will be an online web-platform (www.picse.eu) that will give access to a unique repository of information helping public procurers to understand the best practices, the barriers and the success stories around the procurement of cloud services. The platform will be also a reference point for cloud service providers interested in promoting their services in view of the future call ICT8. It will be one of the main channels for engagement with the project stakeholders and will be central to the PICSE communication and outreach strategy.

The PICSE web platform will have strong links with the existing Helix Nebula website (www.helix-nebula.eu). The aim is twofold: PICSE can extend the Helix Nebula scope to serve the procurement network, on the other side PICSE can leverage the Helix Nebula brand name, which already has high visibility with European research organisations and commercial cloud service providers and its established network. The home page www.picse.eu will embed a button taking to the Helix Nebula home page as shown in picture below.

Figure 4: Detail of the www.picse.eu home page

The PICSE web platform will grow during the lifetime of the project as details of the procurement best practices, barriers, success stories are collected. Social media will be integrated in the web platform.

Table below summarizes the main sections and content of the PICSE web platform that will be developed during the project lifetime:

Section	Sub-menu	Description	Timeline
Home Page		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> PICSE pay-off on the top to describe the project in few lines PICSE scrolling news Buttons dedicated to the PICSE Partner Search and the Online Survey PICSE major stakeholders: the sections explain the benefits for the stakeholders and how they can be part of PICSE Central section dedicated to PICSE & Helix Nebula Latest Tweets Events 	M2
About PICSE	About PICSE	Overview of the project, objectives, consortium	M2
	Who is involved	Partner description	M2
	PICSE Roadmap	Description of the main result of the PICSE project.	M2 - At the end of the project the Roadmap will

			be prominent on the Home Page.
	PICSE Task Force	Description of the PICSE Task Force and its members.	M2
	PICSE & Helix Nebula	Description of the relation between PICSE and Helix Nebula	M2
	Communication Kit	Section containing the promotional material developed by the project (flier, poster, etc.).	M2-M18 - Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
PICSE Partner Search		Section in which cloud providers, public organizations, SMEs and all the actors interested in the ICT8 and ICT36 (focus on cloud) calls can describe their needs, the partners they are looking for the next calls etc. This section will facilitate the dialogue between these interlocutors. Users can post their content (the posts are moderated by PICSE consortium to ensure a high quality service) and leave comments.	M3-M7 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
Learn about...	Learn about...	This section will include guidelines, tips, checklists and examples of implementation for the topics described below.	M2-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
	PCP vs PPI	Series of content pieces providing information regarding the main differences between PCP and PPI.	M2-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
	PCP	Series of content pieces and use cases providing information regarding Pre-Commercial Procurement.	M2-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
	PPI	Series of content pieces and use cases providing information regarding Public Procurement of Innovation.	M2-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
	WP2014-15: ICT8	Series of content pieces providing information regarding the ICT8 Call.	M2-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
	WP2014-15: ICT36 (focus on cloud)	Series of content pieces providing information regarding the ICT36 Call (focus on cloud).	M2-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
News	News	Project news & news items relevant from the project.	M2-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
Events	Events	PICSE & Helix Nebula future events.	M2-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
	Past Events	PICSE & Helix Nebula past events.	M2-M18 Continuous updating and publication

			throughout project lifetime.
	Webinars	Announcement of the webinars and main outcomes. This section will be published after the first webinar and will be continuously updated.	M6-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
In the Media	Interviews & Articles	PICSE & Helix Nebula interviews and articles.	M1-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
	Videos	PICSE & Helix Nebula videos.	M1-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
	In the Press	PICSE & Helix Nebula Press clippings..	M1-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
	Press Releases	PICSE & Helix Nebula Press releases.	M1-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
Publications	Deliverables	PICSE & Helix Nebula deliverables.	M1-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
	Documentation	PICSE & Helix Nebula documents and reports.	M1-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
	Presentations	PICSE & Helix Nebula presentations.	M1-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.
Procurement Wizard		The Procurement Wizard is a decision support tool that can guide the procurer via a series of multiple choice questions to identify suitable options and highlight key aspects that should be taken into account during the procurement process. The tool will be integrated in the PICSE web platform.	M11-M18 Continuous updating and publication throughout project lifetime.

Table 4: PICSE web platform structure

4.1.1 PICSE Partner Search Facility

The PICSE Partner Search facility included in the PICSE web platform will be an opportunity for PICSE to become the reference point of collecting ideas for ICT 8 and ICT36 (focus on cloud) ready for April 2015, will allow demand and supply side to meet their needs and establish new collaborations.

It will be a section of the PICSE web platform in which cloud providers can publish and promote their innovative solutions, public organisations can describe their needs, etc. Users can post their content (the posts are moderated by PICSE consortium to ensure a high quality service) and leave comments.

4.1.2 PICSE Procurement Wizard

The Procurement Wizard is a decision support tool that can guide the procurer via a series of multiple choice questions to identify suitable options and highlight key aspects that should be taken into account during the procurement process. The tool will be integrated in the PICSE web platform.

4.2 Social media campaigns

The creation of PICSE accounts on social media sites can create additional sub-communities and also be a source of back links to the main PICSE web platform. The continuous online presence through prominent social media will inform, guide and solicit procurement practitioners via a growing body of knowledge. An important consideration is that social media accounts require constant updating and monitoring for them to be a real success. All web platform content pieces will be designed to allow the user to share content pieces through social media channels. Value content that will be posted on social networks includes interesting information about the PICSE project such as news, events, reports, etc. and information related to procurement of cloud services, PCP/PPI, ICT8 call, etc.

Two social network accounts were set up at the start of the project with the specific objective of providing an online presence for the project before the European Procurers' web Platform was launched publicly:

- LinkedIn (be.linkedin.com/pub/picse-procure/a7/95/bb4/)
- Twitter (@PICSEPROCURE).

For what concerns PICSE presence on Facebook, the Helix Nebula Facebook page will be used to post most relevant updates from the project. This choice has been done to leverage on the big Facebook community already built by Helix Nebula (406 Likes). The same approach applies to Youtube: PICSE videos will enrich the Helix Nebula YouTube channel by forming a unique repository that can be exploited from both PICSE and Helix Nebula.

4.2.1 LinkedIn

LinkedIn is an important professional website with a focus on professional expertise and business flair/interests. The PICSE LinkedIn account will be used with the following aims:

- Bring on board new relevant stakeholders
- Disseminate the main project outcomes
- Send target messages
- Create and follow discussion groups - Groups can be created on particular themes relating to PICSE.

Relevant LinkedIn discussion groups identified so far: EuroCloud⁵⁷, Supporting public procurement of innovation⁵⁸ (European Commission Enterprise & Industry group), PEPPOL (Pan-European Public Procurement Online) = Public eProcurement for the Future⁵⁹.

⁵⁷ https://www.linkedin.com/groups?mostRecent=&gid=2407468&trk=my_groups-tile-flipgrp

4.2.2 Twitter

A Twitter account, as mentioned previously, has been set up at @PICSEPROCURE.

Twitter will be exploited in particular for reporting on PICSE presence at events such as conferences and workshops; and also to create discussion on topics related to PICSE activities that may be taking place. Regular tweeting can create a sense of activity and movement that is happening and is also a way of imparting PICSE knowledge and expertise (all new content added to the PICSE portal will be tweeted directly on the twitter account).

Twitter hashtag. Dedicated discussions can be launched during PICSE events encouraging participants to contribute. This can be a source of discussion topics during the event and engages participants and also those not attending who can be kept abreast of event topics and discussion. Hashtags can also be used for themes related to service and challenges.

4.3 Other communication tools

Beside the web platform and the social networks, PICSE will leverage on a wider set of communication tools spanning from reports (the main outcomes of the project) to interviews, e-Newsletters, email campaigns and press releases. These communication tools will be leveraged in conjunction with the main project milestones (as shown in paragraph 4.5) to maximize the communication of the PICSE findings and results. Table summarizes the media tool:

Communication material	Description	Quantity
Animated Videos	Animated videos will be created to communicate in an easier way PICSE main results. Two videos will be delivered respectively to promote the outcomes of the case study analysis and of the barriers survey and to promote and speed up the adoption of the new procurement model.	2
Articles on iSGTW	2 Articles on iSGTW will be produced during the project lifetime to ensure the communication of the PICSE results to the scientific community.	2
Best Practices	Best Practices are widely recognised as being very important to foster the uptake of new technologies. They will be collected during the project lifetime and published on the PICSE website. They will cover both science and government.	5
Communication Database	As mentioned in chapter 3 a stakeholder contact database will be set up. The database will integrate a wider communication database including the contact information of the contacts coming from the Helix Nebula newsletter database, coming from social networks, contacts collected at events and contacts coming from desktop research. The database will be constantly updated by Trust-IT and will be exploited by PICSE to create awareness on PICSE results.	1
e-Book	The final Roadmap Report will be made available in an e-Book format to reach the widest number of stakeholders.	1
Email campaigns	Over the lifetime of the project targeted messages for the PICSE stakeholders will	3

⁵⁸ https://www.linkedin.com/groups?mostRecent=&gid=3971446&trk=my_groups-tile-flipgrp

⁵⁹ https://www.linkedin.com/groups/PEPPOL-PanEuropean-Public-Procurement-Online-1876735?home=&gid=1876735&trk=my_groups-tile-grp

	be put together and exploited for the specific engagement campaigns. Individual emails will be also exploited at engagement purpose and to promote the uptake of the final roadmap towards policy makers and public bodies.	
eNewsletters	Targeted eNewsletter will be released in conjunction with the main milestones of the project. The eNewsletter will be exploited to communicate the progress of the project. The PICSE eNewsletter will be sent to the Helix Nebula contact database that will be further enriched by new PICSE contacts. Currently, the Helix Nebula database counts around a hundred contacts.	3
Phone/Written Interviews	Interviews will be conducted with representatives of the public sector to collect information useful for the procurement best practices, success stories and case studies.	10
Press Releases	Press Releases will be delivered in conjunction with the main project milestones to ensure timely communication of the progress of the project.	3
Reports⁶⁰	The main outcomes of PICSE will be 5 reports: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Procurement Barriers Report describes the perceived barriers to the adoption of innovative practices in cloud services procurement with a ranking of the most urgent issues to be addressed. - The PICSE Procurement Model suitable for public national and international research organisations proposes a simpler procurement model of cloud services for the public sector. - The Procurement Case Studies report covers five transnational public procurements giving wide geographical relevance. - The Procurement Best Practices Report addresses Research and Public Administration and a comparison between procurement practices in the public and private sector. - The PICSE final Roadmap contains recommendations and strategic advice for public research organisations for the next five-years. 	5
Video interviews	Short video interviews with the PICSE Task Force members. These video interviews will be published on the Helix Nebula Youtube channel and promoted through the PICSE web platform and social network. The perspective of the task force members will reinforce the overall PICSE communication message.	10

Table 5: PICSE Communication Tools.

4.4 Events

4.4.1 PICSE Webinars

Targeting public sector organisations on the benefits of the new procurement model delivered by PICSE and on the European best practices on procurement of cloud services will be one of the major objectives of the PICSE webinars.

Overall five webinars will be organised by PICSE with the support of other organisations that will be involved case by case. The specific aim of the webinar is to provide specific training sections to complement

⁶⁰ All reports and publications produced by PICSE will be held in zenodo (www.zenodo.org), the OpenAIRE compatible open access repository operated by CERN. The corresponding data gathered as part of the consultations and used as a basis for the reports and publications will also be stored in zenodo once any confidential information has been removed. All publications and datasets will be citable and widely distributed, permitting metrics about re-use to be collected. The material will be linked to the Procurers’ Platform to make it easily accessible.

specific user needs and expertise. The calendar will be made available online (The webinars will start on M2).

The list of participants will be documented after each webinar to prove the success of the webinar. The target audience per each webinar is of around 10 public organisations.

The webinars will be promoted on the most pertinent media channels. Background documentation will be provided by PICSE. After each webinar the recording together with the presentation will be made available on the PICSE web platform.

Below the topics identified so far for potential webinars:

- Seminar at CERN to present Commercial trading of IaaS cloud resources and discuss the different aspects of establishing a cloud services market for the public sector (November 2014)
- Webinar on the barriers of the procurement of cloud services in the public sector (TBD)
- Procurement dry-run with HNX (ATLAS use case) –virtual event to explain in detail the procurement approach and answer questions about specs (TBD)
- Webinar on procurement best practices (TBD)
- Webinar on the procurement model developed by PICSE and demo of the Procurement Wizard. (TBD)

Webinar involving EC personnel on the rules of public procurement + PCP/PPI (TBD)

4.4.2 PICSE final event

A final event will be organised in month 18 to present the project results and actively engage, influence and ensure uptake of the recommendations.

The event will be co-located with Cloudscape VIII (www.cloudscapeseries.eu March 2016, Brussels, Belgium) to save costs and to leverage on the Cloudscape consolidated community.

Cloudscape past editions were successful events, offering interactive workshops and discussions among high-level interlocutors and a big involvement of the major funding agencies. These factors make Cloudscape the perfect candidate for the final PICSE event.

Representatives (mainly procurers) from public research organisations and the public sectors, cloud service providers, policy makers, public bodies, funding agencies and of other European initiatives will be invited to attend the event to reach an audience of around 50 participants. The selection of the participants will be one of the major tasks in order to make sure that all the relevant stakeholders will be present.

The event will be promoted on the most pertinent media channels. Logistics arrangement, background documentation and promotional material will be provided by PICSE.

Figure 5: Cloudscape Gallery

4.4.3 External events

PICSE will leverage on a series of external events to disseminate the project outcomes.

The following table summarizes the events PICSE is planning to attend during the lifecycle of the project:

Candidate events include the Cloud for Europe conference, CSA Congress, the Helix Nebula General Assembly, Cloudscape series and CloudWATCH events.

Event	Date & Location	PICSE Participation	Expected Results
ICT Proposer’s Day 2014⁶¹	9-10 October 2014, Florence, Italy	Presentation of the PICSE project	New contacts with potential stakeholders Project promotion
Cloud Security Alliance EMEA congress 2014⁶²	18-02 November 2014, Rome, Italy	Promotion of PICSE project by CSA	New contacts with potential stakeholders Project promotion
Helix Nebula Initiative 5th General Assembly & PICSE public event⁶³	26-27 November 2014, Frascati, Italy	Procurement of Cloud Services in Europe session with 3 presentations: The 'Cloud for Europe' Procurement Scheme, Linda Strick (Cloud for Europe); Procurement Innovation of Cloud Services for Europe, Bob Jones (CERN), The ESA Stimulus Project & SMEs, Wolfgang Lengert (ESA) Interviews with the HN public research organisations, Presentation of PICSE to the	Engagement of Helix Nebula partners First feedback collection on the PICSE case studies, barriers to procurement and on the interim procurement model

⁶¹ <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-agenda/en/ict-proposers-day-9-10-october-2014>

⁶² <http://www.cloudsecuritycongress.com/>

⁶³ <http://www.helix-nebula.eu/events/helix-nebula-initiative-5th-general-assembly-picse-event-26-27-november-2014-esaesrin>

		Helix Nebula suppliers	
Modernizing the public sector and boosting economic growth through Innovation Procurement ⁶⁴	26 – 27 November 2014, Milan Italy	PICSE presentation	European High Level Event and Networking on PCP&PPI
Public Sector Cloud World Forum ⁶⁵	2-3 December 2014 The Kensington Close Hotel, London	PICSE presentation	PICSE outreach Engagement of new potential stakeholders
Open standards for ICT procurement: Sharing of Best Practices ⁶⁶	3 December 2014, Brussels, Belgium	PICSE participation	Collection of information for the PICSE best practice use cases
Think Cloud for Vendors ⁶⁷	9 December 2014, London, UK	PICSE participation	Collection of information on the market opportunities across the public sector for cloud computing and on the G-Cloud model (how buyers buy, etc.)
Research Data Alliance and global Data and Computing e-Infrastructure challenges ⁶⁸	11-12 December 2014, Rome, Italy	PICSE participation	Networking with high level representatives of member states
C4BI - Public Procurement Conference: Local and regional governance approaches for innovation, economic development and cooperation ⁶⁹	17 December 2014, Brussels, Belgium	PICSE participation	Collection of information on the diverse public procurement approaches and instruments that can impact the capacity of local and regional authorities for promoting innovation both internally and within their local communities. Focus on PPI/PCP, health, lighting
THINK Cloud for Government ⁷⁰	10 February 2015, London, UK	PICSE participation	Collection of information on all the latest information, best practice, opinion and case studies on cloud computing in the digital public sector market. Networking opportunities

⁶⁴ <http://www.helix-nebula.eu/events/modernizing-the-public-sector-and-boosting-economic-growth-through-innovation-procurement-26>

⁶⁵ <http://publicsectorcloud.eu/>

⁶⁶ <http://www.helix-nebula.eu/events/open-standards-ict-procurement-sharing-of-best-practices-3-december-2014-brussels-belgium>

⁶⁷ <http://thinkcloudvendors.com/>

⁶⁸ <https://rd-alliance.org/IT2014EU>

⁶⁹ <http://89.152.245.33/dotnetnuke/procurers/en-us/stakeholdersengagement.aspx>

⁷⁰ <http://www.thinkcloudforgovernment.com/>

			with government officials, IT and procurement professionals, academics, independent analysts, and cloud vendors.
Fifth RDA plenary meeting	8-11 March 2015, San Diego, US	PICSE participation	PICSE outreach Networking opportunities and engagement of new stakeholders
Cloudscape VII⁷¹	9-10 March 2015, Brussels, Belgium	PICSE presentation ICT8 call presentation	PICSE outreach Networking opportunities and engagement of new stakeholders
CSA CEE Summit 2015	11 March 2015, Ljubljana, Slovenia	PICSE presentation	PICSE outreach Networking opportunities and engagement of new stakeholders
Cloud Expo	11-12 March 2015, London, UK	PICSE presentation	PICSE outreach Networking opportunities and engagement of new stakeholders
CloudWATCH Concertation meeting⁷²	25 March 2015, Brussels, Belgium	PICSE position paper & poster	PICSE outreach Networking opportunities and engagement of new stakeholders
Helix Nebula Initiative 6th General Assembly	23-25 June 2015, Geneva, Switzerland	PICSE presentation of the barriers report and of the procurement model	Further engagement of Helix Nebula partners Feedback collection
Datacloud World Congress	3-4 June 2015, Monaco, France	PICSE participation	Collection of information on cloud challenges – integration, procurement, management, hybrid cloud, and security. Networking opportunities and engagement of new stakeholders
LIBER 2015	24-26 June 2015, London, UK	PICSE Paper Submission	Raising awareness of issues in procuring cloud services to public research organisations/libraries and highlighting best practices.
Sixth RDA plenary meeting	September 2015, Paris, France	PICSE participation	PICSE outreach Networking opportunities and engagement of new

⁷¹ www.cloudscapeseries.eu

⁷² www.cloudwatchhub.eu

			stakeholders
Helix Nebula Initiative 7th General Assembly	November 2015, Germany/United Kingdom (TBD)	PICSE presentation of the final procurement model & launch of the Procurement Wizard. Presentation of the first results of the best practices and case studies report.	Further engagement of Helix Nebula partners Feedback collection
Cloud Security Alliance EMEA congress 2015	November 2015, TBD	Promotion of the PICSE new procurement model, of the results of the barriers study and of the first project results related to the best practices	New contacts with potential stakeholders Project promotion
Seventh RDA plenary meeting	March 2016, Japan	PICSE participation	PICSE outreach Networking opportunities and engagement of new stakeholders
PICSE final event co- located with Cloudscape VIII	March 2016, Brussels, Belgium	Presentation of the PICSE final roadmap	Dissemination of the final roadmap.

Table 6: PICSE External Events.

4.5 Communication Gannt

Communication & Dissemination Activites	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16	M17	M18
<i>Communication & Dissemination Database population</i>																		
<i>Set-up of the PICSE static webpage within the Helix Nebula website</i>																		
<i>Set up of PICSE social networks accounts (LinkedIn & Twitter)</i>																		
<i>Launch of the PICSE (www.picse.eu) website</i>																		
<i>Population of the PICSE website (at least 1 news per week)</i>																		
<i>Population of PICSE social networks (at least one post per week per partner)</i>																		
<i>Press release on the launch of the project</i>																		
<i>Video interviews with the Task Force Members</i>																		
<i>e-Newsletters</i>																		
<i>Delivery of 5 webinars</i>																		
<i>Promotion & Awareness Raising on the PICSE project and results through events</i>																		
<i>Fliers Production & Dissemination</i>																		
<i>Pop up banner</i>																		
<i>Poster showcasing PICSE results</i>																		
<i>Roadmap Report e-book</i>																		
<i>Promotion of the findings of the barriers survey - press release</i>																		
<i>Creation of an animated video describing the PICSE procurement model</i>																		
<i>Press Release on the new Procurement Model & the Procurement Wizard</i>																		
<i>Article on iSGTW (promoting the model and the video - Video of the week)</i>																		
<i>Launch of the Procurement Wizard within the PICSE website & Cloud Watch Mobile App</i>																		
<i>Creation of an animated video illustrating the most successful case studies</i>																		
<i>Article on iSGTW (promoting the model and the video - Video of the week)</i>																		
<i>Publication of the best practice report on the PICSE website</i>																		
<i>Press Release on the final Roadmap</i>																		
<i>Synergies establishment with media & stakeholders organisations to leverage as multipliers</i>																		

Figure 6: Communication and dissemination activities (M1-M18)

5. Outreach & visibility

The final aim of the dissemination activities performed by PICSE is to raise awareness around best practices, issues, the new procurement model and the roadmap of PICSE to the biggest audience. To achieve this result the following dissemination activities will be performed.

5.1 Dissemination Database

A dissemination database including all the relevant media channels contacts will be set up and updated during the project lifetime. These contacts will be mainly exploited to announce PICSE events and promote PICSE press releases.

5.2 Press & Media Channels

In support of PICSE awareness raising and visibility a selection of press & media channels will be targeted. Web-based ICT and Technology Media are used as primary sources by ICT professionals (e.g. ComputerWorld, Computer Weekly, eWeek Europe, etc), including broader technology watch (Innovations Report, CORDIS news, 24N.biz) and some targeted at the high-tech research infrastructures (HPC Wire, iSGTW , Supercomputing online, e-IRG Newsletter). Other channels include European press agencies and EU channels, policy channels (e.g. EurActiv, EUObserver, EuropeanVoice.com & European Voice, Europa.eu, EuroParliament, etc.), national press, TV and Radio, media organizations focusing on innovation and public sector, as well as domain-specific sources that reach out to the procurers professionals (i.e. CloudPro, Associations of Procurement, Public Spend Matters Europe, etc).

The list below is not exhaustive and targets may be added to or some removed over the lifetime of the project. At the same time, it is imperative to highlight that not all of these channels may be contacted, they will be selected on a case-by-case basis according to the communication content. In addition, all the partners will exploit at their best also their own press offices and media channels in order to create the right visibility for the project outcomes.

Media Channels	Overview	Target Audience
24n.biz (UK)	ICT news & analysis targeting senior IT decision-making professionals. Press releases and announcements.	Popular ICT & Technology Media Channel
Computer Weekly (UK) (http://www.computerweekly.com/Home/) Europe	ICT news & analysis targeting senior IT decision-making professionals. Press releases and announcements.	Popular ICT & Technology Media Channel
Computer World (UK) (http://www.computerworld.com/) Europe	Technology news and information globally. Press releases and announcements.	Popular ICT & Technology Media Channel
CORDIS Press Service (http://cordis.europa.eu/fetch?CALLER=EN_PRESS) CORDIS Wire (http://cordis.europa.eu/news/home_en.html) Europe	EC-based dissemination channels updated daily targeting enterprise, government and particularly research organisations across EU27 operating in ICT. Press releases and announcements.	Policy channel
eWeek Europe (http://www.eweekurope.co.uk/)	Targets ICT, business and open source communities with its main focus on cloud	Popular ICT & Technology Media Channel

Europe	computing, Green IT, open source, Web2.0, mobile & wireless, networking. Press releases and announcements.	
<i>EUObserver</i> (http://euobserver.com)	A source of EU related news and information, editorially focused	Policy channel
<i>EURACTIV</i> (http://www.euractiv.com)	EU news & policy debates	Policy channel
<i>Government Technology</i> (http://www.govtech.com/)	On line portal focused on IT best practices for public sector in USA.	Popular ICT & Technology for government
Hostingtecnews.com (http://hostingtecnews.com/)	IT Business and News portal covering Cloud Computing subjects.	Popular ICT & Technology & Business Media Channel
<i>HPC In the Cloud</i> (http://www.hpcinthecloud.com/) HPCWire (http://www.hpcwire.com/) International	Web-based channels with international outreach on cloud computing and High Performance Computing with weekly circulation to subscribers.	Popular ICT & Technology Media Channel
<i>Innovations Report</i> (http://www.innovations-report.com/) Europe	Web-based and focused on cross-domain ICT sectors, business and R&D. Press releases and announcements.	Popular ICT & Technology Media Channel
InfoWorld (http://www.infoworld.com/index.html) International	Web-based news channel targeting mainly business & developer communities with frequent coverage particularly of cloud computing. Open Call and conference press releases.	Business Media Channel
<i>iSGTW</i> (http://www.isgtw.org)	International weekly online publication that covers distributed computing and the research it enables. Through iSGTW a scientific readership of over 8700 can be reached.	Popular ICT & Technology & Business Media Channel
<i>Public Sector Executive</i> (http://www.publicsectorexecutive.com/)	Online portal covering the latest public sector news	Popular Public Sector Media Channel
RealWire (http://www.realwire.com)	A social media news release service	Popular ICT & Technology & Business Media Channel
<i>TechWorld</i> http://techworld.com (UK)	Web-based ICT and business news. Press releases and announcements.	Popular ICT & Technology & Business Media Channel
<i>The Information Daily</i> (http://www.egovmonitor.com)	Online publisher of news updates, features, and event content focused on public policy development and implementation.	Policy Channel

Table 7: PICSE media channels.

6. Development of a clear PICSE identity

PICSE will leverage on the experience matured within the Helix Nebula initiative and to underline its strong links with Helix Nebula and its wide network of partners (See paragraph PICSE & Helix Nebula). Therefore, the branding for PICSE reflects that of Helix Nebula. In particular, the colour and the shape of the “e” of the PICSE logo are the same as Helix Nebula.

In order to provide a distinctive PICSE brand which distinguishes it from Helix Nebula, more grey will be used as a background colour on the website.

Procurement Innovation for Cloud Services in Europe

Figure 7: PICSE logo

Different templates have been developed and made available to the consortium for use in all official PICSE communications and announcements, such as a general document template (e.g. deliverable template) and a slide deck template.

This branding will be also used in all project dissemination tools and materials, spanning posters, fliers, pop-up banners, the web platform graphics, etc., to facilitate the communication of PICSE target messages.

In particular during the project lifetime the following promotional and dissemination material will be produced⁷³:

Promotional material	Description	Quantity
PICSE flier	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - 1 flier at the very beginning of the project describing PICSE overall objectives and how stakeholders can benefit from the project - 1 flier update including the first results of the procurement model interim release and the barrier survey - 1 flier to promote the outcomes of the barriers report and of the new procurement model 	4

⁷³ Please note that the promotional material will be used to disseminate PICSE at target events and it has been conceived in order to reflect the progress of the project.

	- 1 flier to distribute at the PICSE final event (M18) containing the results of the project	
PICSE Pop up Banner	- 1 pop up banner to use at events to give visibility to the PICSE main message	1
PICSE Poster	- 1 poster to be used at events to showcase the interim results of the projects - 1 poster to be used at the PICSE final event to showcase the PICSE results	2

Table 8: PICSE promotional material.

All versions of the materials will be made available to the project partners to support their individual outreach activities and to the general public in a “Communication Kit” online repository (www.picse.eu/communication-kit).

7. Impact assessment

The impact of the activities described in this plan will be measured through a core set of **six-monthly key performance indicators (KPIs)** wherever they are quantifiable. Key indicators are:

Ref.	Indicator	Metrics	Target value
KPI1	Web platform impact	KPI1.1 Total and unique visits per month	Minimum target/month defined at month 3 with percentage increases
		KPI1.2 Number of quality news pieces per month	2 new pieces of quality content/month
KPI2	Social Networks impact	KPI2.1 Number of tweets/month	10 per month
		KPI2.2 Number of new Twitter followers	2 per month
		KPI2.3 Number of re-tweets from external twitter accounts	2 per month
		KPI2.4 Number of connections on PICSE LinkedIn	30 per month
		KPI2.5 Number of relevant LinkedIn discussion groups and profiles	3 every six months
KPI3	Communication Tools Impact	KPI3.1 Number of animated videos produced	2 over the project life-time
		KPI3.2 Number of views per videos	200 views per video
		KPI3.3 Number of articles on iSGTW	2 over the project life-time
		KPI3.4 Number of best practices published	5 over the project life-time
		KPI3.5 Number of e-book published	1 over the project life-time
		KPI3.6 Number of eNewsletters produced	3 over the project life-time
		KPI3.7 Number of Phone/Written interviews produced	10 over the project life-time
		KPI3.8 Number of press releases produced;	3 press over the project life-time
		KPI3.9 Number of press clippings achieved	10 press clippings every press releases
		KPI3.10 Number of reports produced	5 over the project life-time
		KPI3.11 Number of video interviews published	10 over the project life-time
KPI4	Events impact	KPI4.1 Number of events attended	5 external events per year
		KPI4.2 Number of new contacts established at external events	3 new contacts for each event
		KPI4.3 Number of organised webinars	5 over 18 months
		KPI4.4 Number of participants per webinar	At least 10 relevant stakeholders per webinar
		KPI4.5 Delivery of the PICSE final event	1 over the project life-time
		KPI4.5 Number of participants at the final event	At least 50 relevant stakeholders
KPI6	Promotional Material Impact	KPI6.1 Number of fliers produced	4 fliers over 18 months
		KPI6.2 Number of posters produced	2 poster over 18 months
		KPI6.3 Number of pop-up banner produced	1 popup banner over 18 months
KPI7	Stakeholders Engagement Impact	KPI7.1 Number of case studies produced	5 over the 18 months
		KPI7.2 Number of contacts in the stakeholders database	50 relevant contacts

Table 9: PICSE KPIs.